

THE MAIN FUNCTIONS USED IN THE ADVERTISING LANGUAGE OF ENGLISH LINGUISTICS

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Abstract. *Today, we live in such a time that all opportunities and conditions have been created for humanity to live in happiness and good luck. It's human nature to want to get what they want, and to brag about it when you get it. Perhaps that's why this character was the reason for the creation of the ad. The article provides a broader definition of advertising and a brief history. Advertising slogans in English, the stylistics used in them, and the appellation are also explained.*

Keywords: *advertising, appeal, slogan, advertising language, advertising history.*

1. Introduction.

When we hear the word advertising, the following images immediately begin to appear in front of our eyes: billboards, banners, tv - short-minute advertisements that are shown around the world, etc. With the help of these advertising tools, people are aware of the newly developed products that fulfill their various types of needs. Any company that is just starting its career will undoubtedly turn to advertising, and in this it will certainly help them with advertising based on a well-thought-out and well-structured script. Nowadays, advertising is ever-present in every society and it has the ability to control people's desires.

The word advertisement means "to draw attention to something" or "to inform someone about something". The purpose of advertising should be easy to remember as well as attract attention. Advertisers use a language that is ordinary and simple to introduce their products to the public, but which makes people interested in the product and encourages them to buy it. In doing so, they organize wordplay and manipulate their underlying meanings. Sometimes, advertisers have to break the rules of the language and take it out of context when necessary, and they also create new words.

Trade advertising is the object of study in many disciplines: marketing, psychology, linguistics, communication theory, influence theory, stylistics and many others. The concept of "advertisement" is defined in the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan, dated 07.06.2022 No.776 "On Advertising" as follows: "advertisement - advertising that is distributed using any advertising means, the content of which is on the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan special information aimed at users and intended to attract attention to the object of advertising, to form or support interest in it, as well as to promote it in the market for direct or indirect profit (income)" [1]. However, advertising has long ceased to be just information. Many researchers study advertising within the framework of psychological, semiotic and communicative approaches.

Material and methods of the study

2.1. The history of the advertisement and how it appeared

The world's first print advertisement was published in China. This ad is about needles, and it was founded in the Song Dynasty. "We take high-quality steel from you and make fine needles from them, ready to use in your home" is written on the bottom and top of the square-shaped white paper with the rabbit logo.

In the Middle Ages, in Europe, people were illiterate and uneducated, besides, they did not know how to read or write. Therefore, it was better for them to draw conclusions based on signs than to understand letters and numbers. To be more specific, people knew which store was in front of them by the picture hanging above it. For example, if there is a sign of shoes above the door of a store, this store is a shoe store; if the bread is standing, it means that it is a bakery [2].

In the period before print advertising, more precisely, at the beginning of the 15th century, there were 3 different types of advertising forms: trademarks, heralds and billboards.

A trademark is a legalized symbol, word or combination of words that is legally documented by the product manufacturer. This form is mainly unique to antiquity. For example, about 4000 years ago, product manufacturers put stone seals on the products they created. By doing this, they have indicated that this product belongs to them.

In ancient times, in towns and villages where almost all the inhabitants were illiterate, heralds carried official announcements and general news through the streets or bazaars shouting to the people. The service of heralds was considered one of the most important types of service before the advent of mass media.

Billboards - this type of advertising also has a long history. In ancient times, the Egyptians, Romans and Greeks placed notice boards in front of their shop doors to publicize important events such as market days. Billboard advertising is also well developed in China. In the Middle Ages, in Great Britain, France, and many parts of Europe, innkeepers were forced to use notice boards in front of their hotel doors. In the Middle Ages, the use of billboards in this direction began to move to other types of trade.

By the 18th century, advertisements began to be published in newspapers in England. The purpose of these early print ads was to promote books and newspapers that had become cheaper due to advances in technology.

In the USA, the demand for newspapers began to grow in the first decade of the 18th century. Later, by 1822, even more Americans than other countries were accustomed to reading newspapers. Half of the content in the newspapers was made up of advertisements, mainly local advertisements. They are aimed at bringing income to each region and developing businesses.

In August 1859, the British pharmaceutical company called "Beechams" was the first to use slogans in advertisements [3].

In 1836, the French newspaper "La Presse" was one of the first to receive royalties for advertising on the newspaper's page. This led to its low price, increase in the number of students, and increase in income. By the 1840s, Palmer had founded a modern advertising agency in Philadelphia. He bought ad space from various newspapers at low prices and made them expensive for sale [4].

Londoner Thomas Barratt is called "the father of modern advertising". Barratt founded his modern advertising company by working on commercials for a soap company and creating slogans for commercials. One of Barratt's famous slogans is: "Good morning. Have you used Pears' soap" - this slogan was popular from that time until the 20th century [5].

Knowing how to effectively use language in advertising is an unparalleled skill, and entrepreneurs who have mastered it will surely witness how customers flock to their products.

Advertisements are a great invention that keeps people aware of good products that meet their needs. Especially now, the service of advertising is incomparable in informing the population

of the products of new enterprises that are laying the foundation stone in business. That's why nowadays advertisements are more and more embedded in our lifestyle.

Language is the most powerful weapon of advertising. A strong company name and label can serve as a product prospect or, on the contrary, can put an end to a budding business. With the advent of social media and web pages, the power of the written word has become more important than ever. Even if people don't regularly, they can often see advertisements for various products on social networks. But as a text-based form of media became dominant, advertising and the way it lived in our lives changed.

In the past, advertising was limited to common things - a bus ad, a 30-second TV ad, half a page in a newspaper. These were comprehensive but not specific. Advertisements are now much more powerful because the power of advertising possesses a great impact on people's desires that you don't realize if it is personally connected to your daily life.

With this invasive strategy in place, how advertising is presented and portrayed needs to be more carefully thought out and planned than ever before. Advertising subliminally manipulates your desires and pretends to be a force in your favor (or at least that's the pretense they give). Judging from this point of view, the power of the language is much more developed and the power of influence has grown significantly compared to previous times.

A.B. can be considered a representative of the semiotic approach. Kostin. In her book "Aesthetics of Advertising" she writes that "advertising in modern society means social relations" [6,7].

Having appeared as an informative message and performing the function of informing about new goods and services, advertising has turned into a means of mass psychological influence on consumers. A well-known representative of the psychological approach to advertising V.I. Shuvanov notes that advertising is a system of psychological means of influencing the consciousness of potential consumers. Their goal is the active promotion of advertised goods or services to the market, as well as the formation of a positive image of the advertising campaign [8].

In communication theory, advertising is considered as one of the forms of communication. In the modern interpretation, the term communication is the socially determined transmission and perception of information within the framework of human communication using various means. Advertising communication refers to one of the types of social communication, as it exists in human society.

Yu.V. Rojdestvensky and E.V. Medvedev consider advertising a type of manipulative communication. In their opinion, "manipulation of the audience is carried out by instilling in the consumer a desire to purchase the advertised product" [9]. In his book "Lectures on General Linguistics" Yu.V. Rojdestvensky classifies advertising as manipulative communication and identifies a special functional style of advertising, which combines the essential characteristics of other functional styles: colloquial-literary, business communication style, scientific and fiction literature and journalism.

"An advertising message creates a certain image (image) of a material object of advertising, which acquires symbolic meaning and begins to exist independently, outside of this advertising message" [9].

Determining the main tasks and functions of advertising causes controversy among its researchers. In our country, the problems of determining the functions and objectives of

advertising were dealt with by B.JI. Polukarov, V.I. Shuvanov, A.B. Kostina, O.A: Feofanov et al. Representatives of different approaches to the study of advertising identify various functions and tasks of advertising. So, V.L. Polukarov believes that the main functions of advertising are economic, social, educational, ideological, educational, political and the function of promoting lifestyle [10].

Within the framework of the psychological approach, the author of the book "Psychology of Advertising" V.I. Shuvanov considers the typical psychological functions of advertising to be:

- creating an image of the company and achieving a favorable attitude towards it;
- creating a brand image;
- dissemination of information about the benefits and advantages of the product brand;
- creating a favorable economic attitude towards the perception of a product or brand;
- the desire for easy recognition of the brand or packaging as the property of the company;
- an attempt to lay the foundations of reputation for subsequent market entry of new brands and new product groups [8].

Thus, most researchers of trade advertising define it as communication between a consumer and an advertiser, the purpose of which is not only to convey a message, inform about the advertised product or service, but also to have a psychological impact on consumers, involve them in the process of advertising communication, and create a favorable image of the advertised product, arouse desire, convince them of the need to make a purchase. We adhere to this point of view. We consider the main functions of advertising to be influencing and establishing contact with consumers.

Results and discussion

3.1. The advertisement language and the analysis of it

When it comes to advertising, there is a strong tendency to utilize imperatives and adjectives. Imperatives are indicative and negative sentences in the form of a command. In many advertisements, the tone of command is very noticeable. When using imperatives, the second person singular form of the pronoun is often used. For example, "buy it just now" - "buy our new product now". Using the imperative "now" makes a person obey the imperative without realizing it; it leaves a deeper mark than the phrase "buy our new product".

Nike's slogan "Just do it" is one of the most famous advertising slogans. This slogan leaves you no need to argue, to think, and simply encourages you to follow it without hesitation. The iconic symbol and the short and easy-to-understand nature of the slogan made Nike be known globally. You don't have to decide anything, just do it, as Nike says.

Quality also has its own role in advertising texts. An adjective is used to encourage you to believe in the product or service being advertised. Adjectives give a deep meaning to an ad, and the right adjectives can turn things around for the better. For example, Subway's "Eat Fresh" combines both an adjective and an imperative. In the sentence "Eat freshly prepared food", the verb "eat" - is a command, and the adjective "fresh" - "clean, new" means that the offered food is healthy, tasty and nutritious. It confirms that it is in a safe and hygienic environment. The quality here is so simple and straightforward that you don't even have to think about it, but when you choose it, it's not hard to understand the power of such a simple word. Offering ideas about safety and health are two of the most common ways to communicate a product to an audience - two concepts that people always want and hope for more of.

Similarly, during Google's advertising for the Pixel phone, "new" is repeatedly used to impress the consumer. This phrase is separated from the text in the ad to make it more memorable for the viewer. As with health and safety, having something new appeals to a technology-driven audience, which is now very common, and creates a legendary "hype" around the product. Simple adjectives such as "new" or "fresh" offer a specific direction in viewing the ad and attracting the consumer's attention.

Many ads also use verbs and adverbs to encourage people to take action. Marmite is clearly distinguished by its infamous slogan "You either love it or you hate it". It forces you to choose between love or hate, both of which are powerful words with fiery emotions behind them.

Also, McDonald's "I am Loving it" - "I love him" creates a sense of solidarity, because each consumer places himself here in the context of "I" and therefore accepts that we all really love him. If an ad says "You love it" it becomes a consumer assumption and works to separate people, McDonald's makes people feel part of the brand and therefore come and eat in their restaurants. It's natural that understanding the simple act of how to reach your audience and using advertising wisely can lead to big changes and breakthroughs.

Apple's "Think Different." - The motto "Think differently" is very creative and well thought out. With this slogan, Apple indicates to the buyer that its product is completely different from others, and thus serves to increase your self-confidence to some extent. In creating such slogans, not only creativity, but also knowledge of human psychology is important. Apple has always valued new ideas and liked to be motivated to contribute to change the world.

Advertising language is wide, colorful and constantly evolving. From customer-specific ads that appeal directly to people, to ads that promise health, love, freedom, security, and other incomparable, broad concepts, how much - how much meaning you'd be surprised how much they exist and how much they affect a person without even realizing it. For example, a well-crafted ad for a product can lead you to buy a product you've never dreamed of buying by offering great deals on that product. You see, a product that you didn't even plan for will appear in your hand in seconds without even realizing it, thanks to a cleverly thought-out slogan.

Coca-Cola, another famous brand that we see a lot at the moment, also uses the slogan "open happiness" - "open happiness". In television commercials, the moment you open the cap of Coca-Cola and drink it, your body feels refreshed and uplifted, and the sound of it shaking when you open the cap will force you to buy it and drink it without realizing it. And the use of the word "happiness" at the end of the ad guarantees that you will be happy when you drink.

4. Conclusion

Thus, it is clear how much work is spent in order for the window of an advertisement to see the face of the world. One of the most demanded claims from copywriters in these processes is eloquence and an excellent knowledge of grammar. These skills can either fulfill the expectations of companies or disappoint them. Therefore, advertising can be considered as a form of culture. Knowing how to effectively use language in advertising is an unparalleled skill, and entrepreneurs who have mastered it will definitely see how customers flock to their products.

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